

ZEUS -

Gestión de seguridad automatizada en redes
5G/B5G mediante la aplicación del modelo de
“closed-loop” basado en arquitecturas ZSM

ZEUS E1

DIRECCIÓN AND DISSEMINATION PLANNING

Title	Direction and Dissemination Planning
Document description	Document and annexes that include, among other things, the planning of activities, coordination between packages, and dissemination efforts.
Nature	Public
Task	A1.1, A1.2, A1.3
Status	F
WP	WP1
Lead Partner	UMU
Partners Involved	UMU
Date	31/07/2023

Revision history	Author	Delivery date	Summary of changes and comments
Version 01	Eduardo Ledesma	15/07/2023	First version
Final Version	Noelia Pérez Palma	31/07/2023	Final Version

Disclaimer:

The Spanish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation and the European Union nextGeneration EU's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commissions cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES	3
LIST OF TABLES	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1 INTRODUCTION	6
2 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	7
2.1. Creation of the <i>CERBERUS</i> brand	7
2.2. Web Communication	8
2.3. Social Media Communication	9
2.4. Project Poster	10
2.5. Communication Talks and events	12
3 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	16
3.1. Publications and technical dissemination	16
3.2. Synergies with other projects	16
3.3. Bachelor, Master, PhD theses and Internships	16
4 EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES	17
4.1. Standardization activities	17

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 - Main and Secondary Logos of the Cerberus Project.	7
Figure 2 - Main and Secondary Logos of Cerberus Subprojects.	8
Figure 3 - CERBERUS Website Homepage.	9
Figure 4 - Details of some of the planned content themes for the various social media platforms of @cerberus_5G.	10
Figure 5 - CERBERUS Project Poster.	11
Figure 6 - Paper presentation.	13

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides an overview of the accomplishments and activities carried out during the implementation of the CERBERUS subprojects in 2022, particularly focusing on communication and dissemination. As these subprojects are interconnected, it has been decided to consolidate the individual reports of each subproject into a single document.

The key achievements in 2022, despite facing delays in the tender process that impacted the full initiation of activities, include:

- Communication:
 - Development of initial promotional materials, such as a website and press releases, utilized both online and at various events to enhance awareness of the project.
 - Active participation in 5G/6G events.
- Dissemination:
 - Submission of a number of papers (considering the limited timeframe and being the inaugural year) in peer-reviewed journals and conferences.

This report reflects the collaborative efforts across the CERBERUS subprojects in advancing communication, dissemination, and standardization activities throughout 2022.

1 INTRODUCTION

CERBERUS pursues, as its main objective, to provide a cognitive, robust, practical, and adaptable security management framework for future events. This framework will be based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, preserving privacy, to monitor, predict, mitigate, and prevent risks and attacks on IT infrastructure. Among the target infrastructures are those encompassing both the Internet of Things (IoT) and so-called Smart Cities, as well as 5G communication infrastructures, with a special emphasis on emerging trends oriented towards 6G.

CERBERUS project is contributing to the following groups of activities:

1. **Communication:** It includes all the activities related to the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's own community. This includes the communication of the research results in a way that is understood by the non-specialist, e.g., the media and the public.
2. **Dissemination:** It includes activities related to presenting its results in a technical community working on the same research field. In general, this will be done through peer-reviewed publications in academic conferences and journals, interaction with other research projects, participation and organization of technical events, realization of exhibitions and technology demonstrations in different conferences and workshops, and the dissemination of standardization activities.
3. **Exploitation:** It covers activities aiming at using the results in further research activities other than those covered by the project, which mostly imply 1) developing, creating and marketing products or processes, 2) creating and providing a service, or 3) standardization activities

CERBERUS project has been structured in 5 subprojects (**ZEUS, HADES, HERMES, HEFESTO and MINERVA**).

2 COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

2.1. Creation of the *CERBERUS* brand

Prior to the creation of a communication plan, the first step is to establish the 'Cerberus' Project as its own recognizable brand, serving as the foundation for all planned communication activities.

The creation of branding and a visual identity, both for the project itself and for all the sub-projects that make up the Cerberus universe, is essential to generate cohesion and consistency in each of the various communications.

Figure 1 - Main and Secondary Logos of the Cerberus Project.

Figure 2 - Main and Secondary Logos of Cerberus Subprojects.

This new brand combines in its logo two key elements of Cerberus: 5G communications and the three heads of the mythological dog Cerberus. This achieves a recognizable and unique visual concept that can capitalize on each communication.

2.2. Web Communication

The project's website has been made publicly available since its inception.

You can access it at the following URL: <https://cerberus.inf.um.es/>. The homepage is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 - CERBERUS Website Homepage.

The developed website serves as a comprehensive platform that provides valuable information about the project and its various subprojects.

Additionally, users have access to dissemination publications and events, details, and other relevant issues in a section dedicated to providing news associated with the project.

There are plans to add a feature with direct access to various social channels. The website and social media will be interconnected, as some posts will redirect to the website and vice versa. This way, users can supplement more specialized information with direct, engaging, and sometimes less technical and more easily understandable content.

2.3. Social Media Communication

The creation and opening of the following social media profiles under the handle @cerberus_5G are planned: LinkedIn, Twitter (X), Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube, in an effort to reach the widest possible audience and allow them to learn about the project.

Content will be duplicated across all social media platforms since, although the platform may change, the sender remains the same. However, each platform has its own characteristics:

- On LinkedIn, being a more professional social network, only content targeting a more specialized audience will be published.

- On Twitter (X), Instagram, and TikTok, content will vary in technicality, ranging from less specialized to more technical. The main idea is to cover a broad and diverse target audience. TikTok, in particular, has the ability to reach a large audience without the need for followers, making it important in the initial stages after the opening of social media accounts.
- Finally, YouTube will serve as a platform for larger-sized videos, housing conferences, congresses, paper presentations, etc.

Figure 4 - Details of some of the planned content themes for the various social media platforms of @cerberus_5G.

2.4. Project Poster

The project poster was created in the first six months of project execution. It contains valuable and concise information about each part of it: Introduction and objectives, a schematic diagram of its architecture, description of each subproject, proposed innovations, and a map of the project's operating environment.

As seen in Figure 5, the poster follows the guidelines set in the branding in terms of form and color.

Figure 5 - CERBERUS Project Poster.

2.5. Communication Talks and events

1. Dissemination Panel at IEEE Future Networks World Forum 2022

UMU has participated in a Dissemination Panel at IEEE Future Networks World Forum 2022. The 2022 IEEE Future Networks World Forum (formerly 5G World Forum) aims to bring experts from industry, academia, and research to exchange their vision as well as their achieved advances towards future networks of 5G and beyond and encourage innovative cross-domain studies, research, early deployment and large-scale pilot showcases that address the challenges of future networks.

The 2022 IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF'22), a hybrid event based in Montreal, Canada, seeks contributions on how to nurture and cultivate future networks technologies and applications for the benefit of society. These systems should unveil a novel mobile network architecture that not only improves physical data rate, but also creates a new ecosystem allowing the deployment of novel services and applications. A key target is to build a novel network architecture that should support not only classical mobile broadband applications and services but also vertical industry (e.g., Intelligent Transport, Industrial IoT, eHealth, etc.) and other future networks-based services. Prof. Antonio Skarmeta has participated in this conference as a Moderator of one of the Panels and Industry forums "FP1: Industrial Forum From 5G to 6G Smart Security Solutions".

2. Workshop on Intelligent Cloud Continuum for B5G Services

Beyond 5G (B5G) applications and services offer unprecedented opportunities for innovation and progress. Nonetheless, achieving such a vision requires a new breed of intelligent mechanisms, protocols and autonomous architectures capable of truly taking advantage of the entire edge-to-cloud computing spectrum.

In particular, cross-domain scenarios, which include multi-cloud and multi-provider, are mostly comprised of heterogeneous technological domains requiring intelligent, efficient and close coordination among all the parts. Such a federated and collaborative view has been set as the path forward for unlocking the required automation and flexibility and achieving the extreme requirements and constraints of such next generation of applications.

In this workshop, Professor Antonio Skarmeta participated as a Program Committee member talking about Secure and distributed computing in the Continuum. IoT devices and

the emergence of 5G in our daily lives are bringing new data-driven and increasingly autonomous scenarios. Next generation networks and the strength of the distributed computing paradigm (edge/cloud) are transforming how services are provisioned, mainly when solutions focus on collaboration and aggregation of resources provided by different entities or organisations, that becomes essential to satisfy the most demanding computation and storage service requirements. However, it also entails challenges such as infrastructure and technologies heterogeneity, which directly impacts infrastructure management and especially security, that usually tends to be relegated to a second place. In this talk we will describe the work carried on several EU project where we use an Intent based/policy-based orchestration paradigm for dealing with heterogeneity, allowing users to request service deployments securely without requiring knowledge about the underlying distributed infrastructure.

Figure 6 - Paper presentation.

3. Sustainability and the Internet of Things

During the week of October 26th to November 11th, Professor Antonio Skarmeta once again represented the University of Murcia by delivering a presentation on the CERBERUS project at the eighth World Forum on the Internet of Things. This event showcased the latest developments in the academic and research community, featuring an extensive program of articles and presentations on cutting-edge technological advancements and innovations across various disciplines driving the utility and vitality of Internet of Things solutions and applications.

4. Webinar on Digital Innovation and Mobile Apps

El pasado 19 de octubre de 2022 el profesor Antonio Skarmeta de la Universidad de Murcia llevó a cabo su presentación titulada Innovación Digital y Apps Móviles: Experiencias en instituciones de educación superior en Iberoamérica. Esta charla formó parte de una serie de Webinars ofrecidos por la empresa chilena Meta-redTIC donde participaron numerosos directivos de empresas punteras de todo el país.

5. Keynote about Challenges in Security Management for 6G Networks at IEEE Future Networks World Forum 2022

Last October 12th Prof. Antonio Skarmeta gave his Keynote about Challenges in Security Management for 6G Networks at IEEE Future Networks World Forum 2022. The 2022 IEEE Future Networks World Forum (formerly 5G World Forum) aims to bring experts from industry, academia, and research to exchange their vision as well as their achieved advances towards future networks of 5G and beyond and encourage innovative cross-domain studies, research, early deployment and large-scale pilot showcases that address the challenges of future networks.

The 2022 IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF'22), a hybrid event based in Montreal, Canada, seeks contributions on how to nurture and cultivate future networks technologies and applications for the benefit of society. These systems should unveil a novel mobile network architecture that not only improves physical data rate, but also creates a new ecosystem allowing the deployment of novel services and applications. A key target is to build a novel network architecture that should support not only classical mobile broadband applications and services but also vertical industry (e.g., Intelligent Transport, Industrial IoT, eHealth, etc.) and other future networks-based services. Prof. Antonio Skarmeta has participated in this conference as an organizer of the Symposium on Security for 5G and Future Networks with his Keynote titled "Challenges in Security Management for 6G Networks".

6. IoT Forum

The IoT Forum was held in the main financial, corporate and commercial center of South America, in the city of São Paulo, Brazil, from October 25 to 27, 2023. As the IoT is a broad and multidisciplinary field, different scientific societies have joined forces with the IoT Forum, making it possible to approach the subject from different points of view.

In this Forum, Professor Antonio Skarmeta participated as a Keynote speaker talking about IoT in the Era of Continuum Computing: Challenges and Opportunities. Making special emphasis on the advent of 5G and the IoT open new possibilities for highly distributed processing capacities from IoT-Edge-Cloud in a continuum: New services require efficient and effective management of computing and network resources which means dealing with huge amounts of data and at different levels of the future network infrastructure. This

distributed context implies the orchestration of resources over the continuum but also provides new security challenges to be considered. In this talk, Antonio traveled along several EU projects and the different challenges and solutions they introduce.

7. 18th International Conference on Network and Service Management

On Wednesday, November 2nd, the "18th International Conference on Network and Service Management" took place in Thessaloniki, Greece, where Professor Antonio Skarmeta delivered a keynote titled "Automated and Secure Lifecycle Management for IoT." The keynote addressed topics such as the recent and well-known attacks and vulnerabilities that IoT has been experiencing, emphasizing the need for automated approaches to the implementation of IoT devices in order to design a framework for the detection, analysis, and mitigation of cybersecurity attacks in IoT implementation.

Indeed, the scale and heterogeneity of IoT devices require self-configuring mechanisms without human interaction to reduce the attack surface. Due to the extensive interconnectedness of such scenarios, a vulnerability in a single device could have catastrophic consequences throughout the network. This is further exacerbated with the deployment of technologies like 5G, where the multitude of relationships and interdependencies among architectural components intensify security management.

The next generation of IoT devices should be capable of self-managing their own security, adapting to environmental conditions, and responding to potential attacks. To lay the groundwork for this evolution, we propose a cyclical methodology that integrates and instantiates the different processes necessary to achieve self-management of the device within its lifecycle management.

8. Symposium on Security in Future Networks

Professor Antonio Skarmeta has participated as an Organizer at the Symposium on Security in Future Networks carried out at the IEEE Future Networks World Forum Conference. It was held from 13-15 November 2023 in Baltimore, MD, USA.

He has also presented an accepted paper authored by Santiago Corcoles Garcia, Emilio Garcia de la Calera Molina, Alejandro Molina Zarca and himself, named "Dynamic ZSM Multi-operator Policy Based Security Framework for B5G infrastructures".

Figure 7 - Paper presentation at FNWF '23.

3 DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

3.1. Publications and technical dissemination

The following paper is currently accepted, pending publication:

- Santiago Corcoles Garcia, Emilio Garcia de la Calera Molina, Alejandro Molina Zarca and Antonio Fernando Skarmeta Gomez. **Dynamic ZSM Multi-operator Policy Based Security Framework for B5G infrastructures**. In: IEEE Future Networks World Forum (FNWF 2023).

3.2. Synergies with other projects

We are currently exploring synergies with two projects:

- RIGOROUS: secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsthwoRthy cOntinUum computing 6G Services. Funded by the European Union's Research and Innovation Programme Horizon Europe under Grant Agreement no. 101095933.
- HORSE: Holistic, omnipresent, resilient services for future 6G wireless and computing ecosystems. Funded by the SMART NETWORKS AND SERVICES JOINT UNDERTAKING (SNS JU) under the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME under Grant Agreement No 101096342.

Joint publications, standard contributions and workshop/event organizations are expected and will be reported in future deliverables.

3.3. Bachelor, Master, PhD theses and Internships

The following theses related to the project are finalized or ongoing now:

- "Artificial Intelligence and offloading techniques in the Internet of Intelligent and Moving Things", Luis Bernal, PhD Thesis. Expected finalization date: 2024.
- "Design and implementation of 5G management intelligent systems", Jorge gallego, PhD Thesis. Expected finalization date: 2024.
- "Vehicular Communications in 5G infrastructures", Maria Dolores Guerrero, PhD Thesis. Expected finalization date: 2026.
- "Diseño y Despliegue de Entornos de Entrenamiento en Ciberseguridad para Sistemas 5G y Blockchain", Marcos López TFG. Finalization date 2023.
- "Diseño y Despliegue de Entorno de Entrenamiento en Ciberseguridad para Sistemas IoT". Luis Rodenas, TFG. Finalization date 2023.
- "Embedded Intelligence in Internet of Things Scenarios", Irene Bru, TFG. Finalization date 2023.

